

Ghost Generator/Battery Cloud Theory

Unnatural phenomenon explained by Caleb Ticer.

Based on repeated cross-referencing and historical evidence, as well as using many peer-reviewed and proven scientific principles, I think that an unbelievable coincidence built out of unforeseeable circumstances is creating the mysterious and weird activity on Lake Lanier. I have allowed myself to broaden my search criteria to include things not necessarily proven, but still reported on the lake, as well as to include more anecdotal evidence. I've begun at the angle of attempting to debunk the paranormal folklore, but now I think that the ghost stories would make more sense than the potential truth I've uncovered if you're not sure which pieces of the immense puzzle go together.

Below is a hypothesis meant to not only debunk the ghost stories and explain them with some tangible and scientific facts, but to potentially call to action those that could test the theory and hopefully save lives (I also outline how and where to test, as well as potential mitigation if correct). It gets weird and jumps all over the place, but that is precisely the reason that the potential has gone overlooked for so long, I believe.

Let's start with a brief history: No, not the Cherokee tribes or Freedmen's Bureau Act settlers run out of the area in the 1830's and 1910's respectively, or the Lady of the Lake, but the mysterious bits that have an explanation, the ESD symptoms, the strange reports of being pulled under or equipment malfunctioning: Dunlap Dam sat on the Chattahoochee river, supplying power to Gainesville and surrounding areas for years. This dam converted running water current into usable electricity, through the use of an alternating current system. Not much else is known about the dam, and some digging needs to be done. A few important notes, George Westinghouse believed in charging more for a system that would last forever and over-engineered many of his products. He and Nikola Tesla designed the Alternating Current (AC) power systems that Westinghouse Electric Co. sold across the country as scaled down versions of their Niagara Falls design, which were meant to last forever. They presumably sold one of these system models to Gainesville, Georgia according to "The Gainesville News" which published on November, 2 of 1910 that the City Council owed a combined bill of \$236.49 to Westinghouse Electric Co., made of three separate bills at the time of the City acquiring the utility assets.

The Gainesville News.

INDUSTRIAL

GAINESVILLE, GA., WEDNESDAY, NOVEMBER 2, 1910.

confined to his room in a state of blindness. Heroic treatment restored the sight in some measure ut from that time until his death Governor Candler could not do much work.

Physical infirmities brought on by his old age, kept Governor Candler indoors during the last ear of his life. He could not get out to mingle with his friends or continue the work of compiling the records he was engaged in for the past few years. He gradually became weaker from day to day, and death resulted last Wednesday.

Hexamethylenetetramine

Is the name of a German chemical, one of the many valuable ingredients of Foley's Kidney Remedy. Hexamethylenetetramine is recognized by medical text books and authorities as a uric acid solvent and anti-septic for the urine. Take Foley's Kidney Remedy promptly at the first sign of kidney trouble and avoid a serious malady, sold by all druggists.

"The Sins Of The Father."

Interesting Facts About Thomas Dixon's New Play Based on Contemporary Race Problem.

Thomas Dixon, author of "The Clansman", has written a new play, "The Sins of a Father", which will be presented under the direction of George H. Brennan at the Lyric Theatre on Wednesday, Nov. 9. In many respects this drama is even more remarkable than "The Clansman", marking an epoch in the dramatic treatment of the race problem.

In "The Sins of the Father" Thomas Dixon presents the ruin that threatened to overwhelm a Southern household from the mixture of races. A beautiful young girl, ward of Major Danie Norton, fiancée of his son Harry, is suspected of being a 'sixteenth-blood' negress. Upon the boy and girl lovers the imputation falls as a crushing blow. The girl's soul revolts at the awful disclosure, but when the Major sets the case plainly before her she sacrifices her own happiness to save her lover's.

But the boy refuses to believe the story despite the strong evidence that supports it. He defies his father and prepares to marry Helen. The Major's

Hall County Strong on Corn.

"The Hall county exhibit was in course of construction yesterday afternoon. J. M. C. Mabry and Marshal Whitehead, who have it in charge, stating their car was late in arriving and consequently they did not get their exhibits ready for the opening day. The Hall county products were not in any one section of the county, but came from different parts. The corn display from this county is by far the big feature of the exhibit. Jim Wheel has some exceptionally fine White Dent corn in this exhibit, which netted him 100 bushels to the acre. Mr. Mabry stated yesterday that the farmers of Hall county are doing a great deal of experimenting and they are getting some good results.

Hall county is noted all over the state for its fine corn and it is on this that the exhibitors expect to carry off first honors, and in addition, will give the others a hot race for the wheat, oats and cotton premiums."

The above is from the Macon Telegraph of last Thursday, and will be seen from the article at Hall county is showing up well at the State fair. Especially is its corn exhibit fine, and it is causing South Georgia folks to "sit up and take notice."

Bury Your Troubles.

Train yourself to keep your troubles to yourself. Don't pour them out upon acquaintances or strangers. It isn't their fault if you have troubles, and they don't want to hear of yours, because they have so many of their own. And, besides—here is a point to consider—if you insist on telling other people of your grievances they will at length come to dislike and shun you because thereby you prevent them from telling their troubles.

—X

COUNCIL PROCEEDINGS.

Council Chamber, Oct. 27, 1910.

Council met in regular session, Mayor Mitchell presiding. Roll called and the following councilmen were present: M. B. Carter, F. M. Loden, G. W. Walker, H. N. Merck, Dr. Robertson and C. H. Bell coming in after the roll was called. Minutes of the regular meeting Oct. 13th, read and adopted.

Petition signed by residents and property owners on the South side of West Washington street, asking that they be allowed to lay a six foot tile walk on that side of the street, was read. On motion council voted to allow said six foot walk to be laid, from the East end of J. E. Jackson property westward to corporate line.

Communication from B. D. Langford asking that the city pay balance due him on the tile walk along property of W. A. Johnson on Green street. Council on motion voted to table the above communication.

A second proposition through the First National Bank to the Mayor and Council proposing to buy the bonds, was read. After some discussion, council voted to accept the proposition provided certain provisions were embodied in the final contract.

Bills for first reading: B. D. Langford, \$64.85; Gainesville Iron Works, \$5.00 and \$11.04; Hardis & Co., \$59.48; Westinghouse Electric Co., \$15.75, \$109.15 and \$11.55.

Bills for second reading read and ordered paid: B. D. Langford, \$230.73; J. E. Hardware Co., \$2.70; Cincinnati Regalia Co., \$4.65; Gainesville Ice Co., \$2.50; C. L. Deal & Son, \$5.80; Castberry Bros., \$5.25; N. va. Electric Co., \$184.25, \$10.00 and \$184.00; Sou. Bell Tel. Co., \$6.00; Bigwell & Gower, \$1.50; W. H. Fuller, \$7.00; G. forth Bros., \$3.25; Geo. F. East, \$33.50; W. J. & E. C. Palmour, \$17.00; H. L. Gaines, \$2.15, 40c. and \$3.50.

There being no further business, council on motion adjourned.

R. D. Mitchell, Mayor.
Jas. H. White, Clerk.

How To Stop A Stubborn Cough

We don't mean just stop the irritation in your throat—but cure the underlying cause.

Cough syrups cannot do this. It takes a constitutional tonic body

RO BAKING
MAKES
HOT F
Also Rolls
Crusts
Send for Royal
Cook Book

A Joke on the "C

Old man Jones and his son day and sold their hogs. T each of them a check on th Now the old man was just "if it is just the same to you and asked John if he wanted just as soon have the check father to keep for him but lost his pocket book and all it could not be found. The forever. But say, John car him the check and told him

The reports suggest that sometime in 1935, the dam failed. The dam's specific purpose at that time was to power the electric rail-car system set up at a resort nearby as well as for some small communities and farmland in the valley that would eventually become Lake Lanier. Reports also indicate an attempt to repair the dam in 1936, before ultimately being considered unviable and abandoned. The dam sat unused until the USACE (US Army Corps of Engineers) created Lake Lanier in 1956. However, a coincidence lines up here: in 1935, the FPC (now the FERC) created licensing requirements for hydroelectric operations, and I believe that Dunlap was unable to meet those standards. For the record, the FERC did not make guidelines on proper de-energization of derelict hydroelectric/hydrodynamic systems until 1994, almost 60 years later.

Those guidelines were followed at the Bull Run Project (Oregon, 2007-2008), the Condit Dam (Washington, 2011), and the Edwards Dam (Maine, 1999). All places where

these phenomena don't happen. That isn't proof, just a note. The procedure guidelines were not even considered in the time that Dunlap was left abandoned, and therefore those guidelines most likely weren't followed. This can potentially be proven through very easy testing. But it's almost fully proven when you keep connecting the dots. Many of the weird and unexplained things I've been able to find involve swimmers, divers and more feeling like they can't breathe, and feel like they are being pulled under. Well, these symptoms could be explained by Electrical Shock Drowning (ESD), which has also happened on the lake under weird circumstances before (1994, 2023.)

The Dunlap Dam at the time, created the lake that it sat behind, so the potential electrical hazard risks would have only been noticeable at Warner Lake before that. However, I don't believe the perfect storm aligned correctly until years of sediments collected under Lake Lanier. The sediments in the area, it can be assumed, are very mineral rich. Local areas include Silver City and Coal Mountain. If the silt from the lake walls is ion-rich, and the fine silts somehow make their way into the system or around an exposed ground, or potentially into degraded insulation of the system, the entire silt cloud could potentially become energized. If stirred, the particles suspended in the layers of the water could act as a conductive antenna medium to produce electrical currents, if some were to somehow be introduced.

If the Westinghouse system was never fully recovered or salvaged, the potential of it catching current underwater exists, especially if a current is introduced in the underwater river channel where the Dunlap Dam sits when the Buford's spillways open. Even the slightest rotation of the turbine would send a ghost current through the system. If that happened at the end of an exposed wire at the same time as a small gas bubble were to cross paths with it, the current could potentially produce an arc, which would explain the very rare accounts of lights under the lake, and even explain why they are so rare.

Lake Lanier: Anomalies Overlaid with Historic Power Infrastructure

Lake Lanier Electrical Anomalies & Pre-Flood Power Corridors (With Cluster Ellipses)

If this happened at a time of increased current along the Lakebed, and if the silt pile has collected large enough over the period of time to spread further in the water, the ghost current could potentially leak through an exposed wire, or an unsuccessful grounding system into what is now essentially a battery cloud. As swimmers kick and play, the wakes and currents they create mixing with the potentially-energized underwater currents, they become surrounded by some of these particles and then, as the current pulses through the conductive antenna, they experience mild symptoms of ESD such as the neuromuscular paralysis that makes swimmers feel as if their leg is being pulled under, instead of surrounded by ion-rich microparticles conducting the current produced by a ghost generator through a battery cloud. The tingling in the water, the biting and magnetization of anchors, the unusual drift patterns of boats, even the very few reports of failed or malfunctioning monitoring equipment that divers and fishers use near the old Dunlap power corridor all at least lean on a possibility of this theory being accurate.

Like I said above, if this idea is broken down into the bits that make it up, all of this has been proven to be possible, but the correct environment has never existed before to produce this exact situation, which is why no one could have foreseen this potential. There is evidence that AC currents can leak through old power systems with minimal effort, it's been proven that ion-rich water can conduct electrical currents, and it's been proven that gas bubbles interacting with electrical arcs can produce lights underwater briefly. Also, the fact that most of the incidents happen in summer isn't just because that is when most visitation to the site occurs, but because the warmer water has been proven to increase conductivity and therefore the range of possible events.

As for the testing to prove this theory, it would be very non-invasive I believe and could be completed quickly, potentially saving more lives. Silent-drift electromagnetic monitoring alone just in a few separate water conditions could prove it more or less. Cold water and warm water differences in Electromagnetic field comparison as well as electromagnetic monitoring before, during and after Buford Dam release cycles should show slightly elevated electromagnetic levels in the lake specifically when the water is warm and during or directly after the dam releases water. As long as there were no other electric materials on, you could trust the findings, which is why silent-drift would be required when measuring the conductivity. After you have that, you can compare that with mirrored testing in another area of the lake far away from the Dunlap power corridor and cross-reference your findings. The second test should show the other areas have no increase in the exponentially lower electromagnetic activity in the water. For more accurate readings, do each test twice, above and below the thermocline layers. Dunlap being below that level means the degradation of the electrical systems would happen at a slower rate, and there's fewer biological factors messing with the old dam at that depth as well, giving more credence to the theory. However, the most important reading would be about 90 feet below the surface, near the dam to see if it is still active at all. If you find that the grounding system is still intact but there is power, follow further down the grid to find the leak.

In the above illustration (crude, I know, sorry; I'm no artist) You can see that when there is a current strong enough to move the turbine, it's almost guaranteed to also be strong enough of a flow pattern to suspend the silt and move it through the water. For this reason, I do believe that testing will need to occur below and above the thermocline layers. The majority of the testing could be completed with a simple EMF detector attached to a boom with two electrodes meant to react to any current in the water. The picture above shows that the grid extended down through the valley for years before the dam was closed down. Many readings at different depths and times would be required, but this makes the hypothesis testable in weeks instead of years, potentially saving more lives.

Now, the process may be costly, especially if this hypothesis is correct. However, this is a new phenomenon and acts as proof of concept for another theory which could make those costs negligible: If this accident could be controlled and managed safely, putting electro-induction arrays behind hydrodynamic power collection systems could

harness the potential current that could be purposely produced from the water flow when we open spillways. Not only could this excess power now fully run the dam operations nationwide, meaning almost the entire input of energy is free, but the energy output from each system could potentially increase. Further testing would be required and of course this is not necessarily dependent on the hypothesis above being correct, but initial estimates are a 5-7% increase in power production minimum if you only cover the direct area behind the water intakes, more if moved back further so more collection turbines can benefit from the flow current, though the further back the turbine, the less of the flow power it can harness. This part of the theory is not affected by the potential results of conductivity/voltage gradient testing at Dunlap Dam, but rather proven to be viable if the theory is correct, and also would be run solely on the flow power of the dam in front, creating free energy from the excess current.

If this hypothesis is accurate, the fix is actually quite simple: On a day when the water is cold, and Buford dam is closed, have EMT's trained in ESD treatment standing by, and send divers down to de-energize the dam the way it should have been 90 years ago, after Euro-American settlers spent over 100 years keeping any neighbors of color out of the stolen valley they received through a land lottery that ultimately started the Trail of Tears, which they then left abandoned and sold back to the government at a later date. We need to see if the grounding system is still active, and if not, fix that, and we need to go through the proper de-energization protocols as outlined by the FERC. It isn't fair that to this day, a relic of the past is sitting beneath the waves and still being violent in a way that people

can't understand, considering most people don't know that Buford Dam even has a big brother. The fact is, the ghost stories are true: but the ghost is a machine.

I feel it necessary to add, as the potential discoverer of this phenomenon, that it is no one's fault. There is no way that anyone could have assumed this would happen until it did, and as I stated at the beginning, a ghost story is more believable without further testing. I'd also like to add, the reason my testing doesn't mention diving in that area until confirmed is because of the potential risk if I'm right to other divers who aren't prepared to go into that environment specifically to mitigate the risk for others. I don't want to cause people to think they need to cover their butts and put that ahead of public safety as the priority. In fact, the only one who could have potentially predicted this was Thomas Edison who warned us about the dangers of alternating currents if left unchecked, and passed away before any of the variables in this equation existed. If he could read this theory, he may feel vindicated.

-Caleb Ticer

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Item vintage Lake Lanier map w/ 1933 aerial view before impoundment, 2 sides, RARE (image 4/5)
Image 4 of 5